

ORGANIZATION OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING THE CASE METHOD AT THE UNIVERSITY

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The case method is an effective means of increasing the effectiveness of teaching in higher education. It has significant functionality, meets the demands of the revolution in education. At the same time, it differs not only in the educational effect associated with obtaining professional knowledge and skills, but also in the impact on the socialization of students, the formation of their personal qualities.

The main advantage of the case method is that it allows you to realize to the greatest extent the creative potential of the teacher. It seems to be by no means a rigid scheme for the implementation of training, it is rich and diverse. As a constantly evolving method, it needs constant interaction with the methodology that develops its concept, saturates its content. In fact, the case method forms a progressive paradigm of teaching activity, which is characterized by a higher level of efficiency and meets the requirements of the time. However, the case method is not universal. They should be used not instead, but together with classical educational methods, that is, situational analysis should not replace, but complement lectures, seminars and practical classes.

As for the methodology of work using the case method itself, the following methodological tips should be followed when organizing a discussion:

1. Plan discussions in groups of 10-25 people to facilitate discussion and ensure a free exchange of ideas.
2. When determining the time limit, consider the nature of the topic. More complex topics may require more time to discuss.
3. Arrange the seats for the panelists in such a way that everyone can easily see and hear each other. The best option is an arrangement in the shape of a horseshoe or in a circle.
4. Help the group choose a topic for discussion and allocate enough time to research and study it.
5. Explain to the audience how to prepare for the discussion so that the discussion time is used as efficiently as possible.
6. Always take a few minutes at the beginning of a discussion to explain its purpose to the participants.

7. Give participants instructions on the process and procedure of the discussion: how they should behave, what role you will perform.
8. At the beginning, set the discussion in the right direction. Ask a question and proclaim theses based on educational goals.
9. Control, but do not slow down the discussion. You may have to make a plan in advance how to guide the group, and act strictly according to this plan.
10. Effectively control the behavior of the group leaders, give them the opportunity to learn to respect and appreciate the views and contributions of others.
11. Deliberately ask silent participants what they think about the issue under discussion, or how they would act in this or that situation.
12. At a favorable moment, summarize the discussion. Invite each participant to formulate a short summary of the discussion or ask one or two participants to present their version to the audience.

The implementation of the implementation of the case method in an educational institution requires special and hard work. Situational methodology should undergo a period of adaptation, as a result of which it can be easily "integrated" into the current educational process. One of the most important aspects of teaching foreign languages is the use of cognitive and semantically oriented teaching methods. The new cognitive-discursive approach, which has been rapidly developing in recent decades, involves the consideration of linguistic phenomena in inseparable connection with culture, the linguistic picture of the world, and the conceptualization of the basic forms of the existence of reality. Communication, as it is known, is an essential condition for a person to know the surrounding reality. Representatives of cognitive linguistics believe that each language is equivalent to a certain system of concepts through which native speakers perceive, structure, classify and interpret the flow of information coming from the surrounding world. The identification of concepts and their connections allows us to take a fresh look at the communication process, which can be considered as the interaction of the conceptual systems of the addressee and recipient.

The process of forming a "secondary linguistic personality" is connected not only with mastering the verbal code of a foreign language and the ability to use it in real communicative situations.

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